

Progressive failure modelling of notched composite laminates and its experimental verification

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ABSTRACT

Failure initiation and propagation in notched cross-ply laminates was extensively studied. First, a stiffness reduction model, which is represented by a local stiffness reduction and local stress redistribution, is introduced to formulate the matrix-dominated failure in fibre reinforced plastic (FRP) laminates. A one-step stiffness reduction is adopted to transfer global average stiffness degeneration into local stiffness reduction. Then, a laminate is physically described as a sequence of stacked homogeneous orthotropic layers with thin interfacial layers in between every two neighboring layers. Constitutively, it is assumed that the laminate is made up of homogeneous orthotropic layers before and after matrix-dominated failure occurs. Consequently, the average reduced layer stiffness as a function of the applied strain is separated from the reduced stiffness of the laminate. Next, a finite element model (FEM) was created by which the failure evolution is evaluated. Combined with a group of stress/strain based failure criteria, this approach was used to study the matrix-dominated failure in notched cross-ply laminates, including transverse cracking, notch-induced split (NIS) and notch-induced delamination (NID). The numerical results show good agreement with the experimental measurements.

1. Introduction

The anisotropic and heterogeneous features of composites result in a variety of possibilities to failure. However, the failure behavior of these anisotropic inhomogeneous materials is insufficiently understood. In traditional strength models [1-6], the consequence of the matrix-dominated failure in composites is not adequately handled, or even completely neglected. Furthermore, strong interaction/intersection exists between different types of failure. The interaction and its effect on the evolution of the matrix-dominated failure and on ultimate failure of a notched composite laminate have not been sufficiently addressed so far.

The well-known point stress model (PSM) and the average stress model (ASM) proposed by Whitney and Nuismer [2, 3] are rather successfully used in engineering, see Figure 1. In PSM, it is assumed that failure occurs when the local stress in the loading (x -) direction at a certain distance (d_0 characteristic length) from the notch root reaches the unnotched strength of the composite, see Figure 1 (a):

$$\sigma_x(0, \mathbf{y}) \Big|_{y=R+d_0} = \sigma_0 \quad (1)$$

In ASM, it is supposed that failure occurs when the local average stress in the loading (x -) direction over a distance (a_0 characteristic length) from the edge of the notch root attains the unnotched strength of the composite, see Figure 1 (b):

$$\frac{1}{a_0} \int_R^{R+a_0} \sigma_x(0, \mathbf{y}) d\mathbf{y} = \sigma_0 \quad (2)$$

Both models have two parameters, σ_0 and d_0 in PSM and σ_0 and a_0 in ASM. However, it is questionable that the claimed material constants (characteristic length), d_0 and a_0 , are real material constants. In fact, they are geometrically notch-size related parameters. Karlak [5] concluded that the characteristic length, d_0 , in the PSM is not a material constant, but proportional to the square root of the notch radius. He modified the criterion according to this conclusion. One more point is that the notch effect, e.g. stress/strain concentrations, will become weaker or even vanished after a matrix crack/split/ delamination near the notch has been initiated. It is more reasonable to study the local damage effects instead of the notch effects after local failure is initiated. Stress/strain based approaches require a correct prediction of the stress/strain components at the crack-tip. Without solving the singular stress problem at the crack-tip, these stress-based approaches are extremely doubtful in failure prediction.

Figure 1. Schematic representation of (a) point stress model (PSM), and (b) average stress model (ASM).

This paper will present an alternative approach based on a progressive failure model to study the formation and propagation of matrix dominated failure in cross-ply laminates. First, a stiffness reduction model is introduced to formulate the matrix-dominated failure in FRP laminates. A one-step stiffness reduction is assumed to transfer global stiffness degeneration into local stiffness reduction. Then, a laminate is physically described as a sequence of stacked homogeneous orthotropic layers with thin interfacial layers in between every two neighboring layers. After that, numerical simulations were performed to study the failure process of different types of laminates. Finally, the simulated failure behaviour is compared with the experimental observations.

2. Model development

2.1 Experimental observation

When a notched cross-ply laminate is under tensile load, various types of matrix dominated damage will occur in the laminates, including transverse cracks, notch-induced splits (NIS) and notch-induced delamination (NID), see Figure 2. In the Figure, $2t$ is the total thickness of the laminate and $4n$ is the total layer number. The transverse cracks occur in the very early stage of loading [8, 9], and cause stiffness degradation. Because of the NIS, notched cross-ply

laminates show peculiar failure behaviour: its predicted strength is always lower than the observed values.

Figure 2 The multi-forms of failure in different notched cross-ply laminates $[0_n/90_{2n}/0_n]$ under static tensile load in the length direction, where $4n \times 0.125 = 2t$. The notch-width aspect ratio is defined as $\mathcal{R} = 2R/W$, where R is the notch radius and W is the width of the specimen.

The experimentally observed stiffness degradation for the laminates is presented in Figure 3(a). The reduced laminar stiffness in the transverse direction can be estimated from the reduced stiffness of the laminate, by assuming that the tensile Young's modulus in the fibre direction of the longitudinal laminae remains unchanged, using simplified classical laminate theory (CLT).

Figure 3 (a). Observed stiffness reduction behaviour caused by transverse crack.

Figure 3 (b). Assumed stiffness degradation of transverse layers to describe the effects of a transverse crack.

2.2 One step stiffness reduction assumption

Based on the experimental observation, a one-step stiffness-reduction mechanism is assumed (see Figure 3b) to convert the average layer-scale (global) stiffness reduction into local stiffness reduction: once local failure occurs, the local stiffness at the failure site reduces to its minimal values:

$$E_{ij}^{res} = (1 - \alpha_{ij}^{\max}) E_{ij}^0 \quad (3)$$

where E_{ij}^{res} and E_{ij}^0 are the residual stiffness and the original stiffness, respectively. $(1-\alpha_{ij}^{max})$ are a group of scalar parameters, which represent the normalized residual stiffness. Obviously, α_{ij}^{max} stands for the maximum normalized stiffness losses:

$$\alpha_{ij}^{max} = \max \left\{ \alpha_{ij}^L (\varepsilon_{ij}) \right\} \quad (i, j = 1, 2, \dots, 6) \quad (4)$$

2.3 Constitutive law

The local stiffness reduction leads to a local stress redistribution

$$\{\Delta\sigma\} = \{\sigma\}^0 - \{\sigma\}^{red} \quad (5)$$

where $\{\Delta\sigma\}$, $\{\sigma\}^0$ and $\{\sigma\}^{red}$ stand for the changes of the stresses, the stresses without stiffness reduction, and the stresses calculated with reduced stiffness. The effective stresses in the softened materials can be calculated from the original stiffness matrix and the residual stiffness, combined with the local stress redistribution:

$$\{\sigma\}^{red} = \sum_{k=0}^i [C]^0 \{\Delta\varepsilon\}^k + \sum_{k=i+1}^{\infty} [C]^{res} \{\Delta\varepsilon\}^k - \{\Delta\sigma\} \quad (6)$$

In this way, the local stress redistribution will be determined by the stiffness reduction and the local strains.

2.4 Failure criteria

The failure criteria are applied on a layer-scale to predict where and when a local failure event will occur. Together with the local stiffness reduction model, these criteria will determine how a local failure event will proceed. A local failure event will start when the relevant local stress components or their combinations reach their reference (critical) values. The general form of failure criteria in terms of the local stresses can be written as:

$$f(\sigma_{ij}^L; X_{ij}^L) - 1 \geq 0 \quad (7)$$

where σ_{ij}^L is the local stresses and X_{ij}^L is the corresponding critical values. The superscript “L” indicates that the stresses are local values. Under the driving of the applied load, the local material degradation will occur abruptly, while global failure will occur accumulatively and will proceed progressively.

3. Model study

3.1 Bridging fibres in mode I and mode II cracking

To show the bridging fibres between the crack surfaces, and hence to get a better physical sense of the fibre bridging effect, Figure 3 presents two pictures from a double cantilever beam (DCB) test and from a tested end-notched-flexural (ENF) specimen. Figure 4 (a) presents the bridging fibres (side-view) between the crack surfaces in mode I cracking. While Figure 4 (b) illustrates the bridging fibres between the two crack surfaces of an ENF test sample (side-view), after it is tested in mode II cracking. This type of bridging effect is rarely reported. The observations indicate that fibre-bridging effects do exist in mode II cracking. Therefore, it may be adopted as a generally existing phenomenon in cracked composites.

Figure 4 Observed bridging fibres between the crack surfaces in DCB test and in ENF test: (a) top-view and side-view of a DCB test, (b) side-view of a tested ENF specimen.

3.2 Dependence of the local stresses on the reduced stiffness

For understanding the effect of the local reduced stiffness on the calculated local stresses, and also to show the necessity to convert the measured global critical load into local critical stresses, a simple mode II delamination (of an orthotropic laminate) is studied. Figure 5 illustrates the configurations of the specimen in details: $L = 50$ mm, $a_0 = 35$ mm, $B = 15$ mm ($a_0/L = 0.7$). From beam theory [10], it is known that a stable crack propagation is expected when the ratio, a_0/L , is higher than 0.7. The loading speed is 0.5 mm/min. First, the global critical displacement of an ENF beam is experimentally measured, which is 3.3 mm in deflection. At this global load, the mode II interlaminar delamination starts to propagate. Then, the local critical stresses in accordance with this global critical load are numerically determined with different reduced stiffness parameters, from 0.1 % to 10 % of the original values. Finally, the local critical state is given by a group of curves that represent the dependence of the local critical stress on the residual stiffness, and these curves are then applied to predict the interlaminar delamination.

Figure 5. The configurations of the end notched flexure (ENF) test specimens: $L=50$ mm, $a_0=35$ mm, $B=15$ mm. Loading speed is 0.5 mm/min.

The local stresses at the delamination front depend on the reduced stiffness, and hence the local critical stresses will be a function of the local reduced stiffness parameters. To show the dependence of the local stresses on the residual stiffness, Figure 6 (a) illustrates the normalized shear stress against the average stress at the delamination front in the undamaged material as a function of the assumed reduced stiffness. One can draw several conclusions from the stress distribution. First, the calculated stress is a function of the reduced stiffness. Secondly, the maximum stress appears at the edges of the specimen. Thirdly, at high residual stiffness, the influence of the residual stiffness on the calculated stress becomes less significant. Krueger [7] published similar stress distribution for mode II delamination by using combined shell/3D elements technique.

The dependence of the local stress on the local residual stiffness means that the unique local critical state (characterized by local stresses or strains, or other local variables) should be determined together with the reduced stiffness. Figure 6 (b) presents the calculated crack-tip stresses as a function of the local residual stiffness at the global critical condition: 3.3 mm deflection. One of the three curves represents the element average values of the in-plane shear stress, one represents the maximum values at the integration points, and the other is the stress of the extrapolated values from the integration points. Several conclusions can be drawn from the calculated stresses. Firstly, when the reduced moduli tend to zero, the $r^{-1/2}$ type singularity can be achieved approximately. This means that the present method is consistent with other approaches in dealing with the local stress singularity. Secondly, the local critical stress indeed depends on the reduced shear modulus, which changes from 0.1 % to 10 % of the original value in the simulation. Consequently, the global critical load condition has to be converted into a local critical condition, in terms of the local reduced stiffness and the local stresses. In this way, the problem caused by mesh dependence might effectively be solved if an identical mesh is applied. Thirdly, a relatively higher residual stiffness, i.e. 5 % to 10 % of the original values, results in a piece of the curve that is almost horizontal, at which the local stresses become less sensitive to the local reduced stiffness. Therefore, one may reasonably expect that such a stiffness reduction will diminish the mesh dependence and help to ease the requirement of applying exactly the same FEM mesh.

Figure 6 (a) Normalized shear stress at the crack-tip with different residual stiffness.

Figure 6 (b) Calculated critical stress at crack-tip with residual stiffness: the global critical deflection is the same: $d = 3.3$ mm.

4. Model application

4.1 Failure modeling of a special type of ENF tests

In the test, a special type of cross-ply laminates is used to avoid the strong fibre bridging effect in mode II delamination. The laminate is constructed such that a very thin transverse layer (about 0.1 mm in thickness) is placed in-between two longitudinal layers. In this case, the delamination will propagate in the thin transverse layer, or at the interface. The initial crack length is 35 mm, which is 70 % of the half span of the beam. Two types of delamination growth behaviour are observed. One of them is characterized by a stable delamination growth as that shown from test 2 and test 3, which is represented by a relatively constant slope in Figure 7. The crack growth rate against the applied deflection (the slope of the curves) is more or less constant, about 85 mm per millimeter applied deflection. Another type of delamination shows (test 1 and 4) a strong resistance in initiating the delamination from the original crack. After its initiation, the crack shows a sudden growth in conjunction with an abrupt force decrease. After such a jump, the crack growth becomes stable again, and propagates at about the same rate, typically as that shown from test 1 and test 4 in Figure 7.

The FEM model is constructed such that it reproduces the geometrical configurations of the tested ENF beam. The thickness of the transverse layer is 0.10 mm. The critical shear strain used to induce the damage is 0.005. The reduced moduli are 10 % of the original values. The simulations show a stable crack growth in the ENF beam. Then, most importantly, the predicted delamination growth rate shows quite good agreement with the first type of delamination growth behaviour. The fitted delamination growth rate from the simulation is 77.12 mm per millimeter applied deflection. This result indicates that the present model can be used quantitatively to simulate the stable growth of a failure event in a laminate.

Figure 7. Delamination growth in ENF tests and the model simulation.

4.2 Formation of transverse cracks and stress concentration evolution

As an overview, Figure 8 presents a simulated damage pattern of a notched cross-ply laminate at about 40 MPa tensile stress. The darker areas represent the damaged parts in 90° layers where extra strain is induced. Such an area may be considered to be analogous to a crack. The transverse cracking is highly localized and characteristic in such a notched plate: the first several cracks initiate always from the notch. One of the eminent attributes from the present modelling is that the model predicts a separate transverse damage pattern parallel to the fibre direction in 90° layers. Extra local deformation is induced by the material damage in transverse layers.

Figure 8. Simulated transverse crack evolution, viewed from the midplane of the laminate. The applied average strains are 0.000704, 0.000843, 0.00112, 0.00125, 0.00151, and 0.00178 for (a), (b), ..., and (f), respectively.

A result of the matrix cracking in 90° layers is a local and global stress redistribution in the laminate. Figure 8 illustrates the evolution of the stress concentration in 0° layers with the development of transverse cracking. The initial part of 9 (a) is then magnified in Figure 9 (b). The maximum stress concentration in 0° layers is about 5.6 during elastic deformation, while the corresponding value raises to about 6.5 after FTC started, and it is still growing up with the development of transverse cracking in the transverse layers. This stress concentration may eventually reach a value as high as 7.8 after the transverse cracks are fully developed in the transverse layers. Obviously, this extra stress concentration depends on the thickness ratio between the 90° layers and the 0° layers. There is no analytical solution to predict the additional stress concentration caused by transverse cracking. Nevertheless, it should be noted that the effects of other damages on this stress concentration is not yet included, which may act favorably to reduce the stress concentration in reality. It should also be mentioned that the increase of the stress concentration factor is a kind of "locally accumulative effect" of all transverse cracks.

Figure 9 (a). Stress concentration (at $x = 0$) at the mid-surface of the 0° ply as a function of transverse cracking, $2t = 1$ mm and $2R/W = 0.2$. (b). Enlarged initial part of (a).

4.3 Notch-induce splits and stress concentrations

A study is performed to learn the effect of the critical strain on the NIS growth. The influence can be examined in two aspects: the predicted NIS onset strains and the growth rate of the NIS. Figure 10 (a) presents the influence of the critical in-plane shear strain on the growth of the NIS in three cases: $e_{12} = 0.0025$, $e_{12} = 0.005$, and $e_{12} = 0.01$ for a 1 mm laminate with $\mathfrak{R} (= 2R/W) = 0.25$. The whole NIS growth is not a linear function of the far-field applied strain. It is very clear that the NIS growth rates (the slopes of the fitted lines of the initial parts) get higher as the critical strain decreases (they are 20.97, 10.27 and 5.45 for $e_{12} = 0.0025$, $e_{12} = 0.005$, and $e_{12} = 0.01$, respectively). The growth rate is approximately linearly proportional to $1/e_{12}$ in the early stage of loading. Figure 10 (b) shows the growth of the NIS against the normalized strain, which is defined as ratio of the applied strain to the critical strain. It can be seen that the NIS growth against the normalized strain is almost the same in the three cases.

Figure 10 (a) NIS growth against the applied strain.

Figure 10 (b) Simulated NIS growth with the influence of critical in-plane shear strain.

The applicability of the present modelling approach can be established by comparing the simulated damage patterns with that from the experimental observations. Figure 11 (a) presents three experimental pictures at different applied strains to show the damage development. The corresponding simulated damage patterns at about the same applied strains are shown in Figure 11 (b), where a critical in-plane shear strain 0.005 is used in the simulation. The resemblance is obvious when the following features are considered: NIS occurrence positions, NIS length, local delamination positions and growth manners. The similarity in the damage patterns indicates that the present progressive simulations can approximately reproduce the evolution of the matrix-dominated failure process in such notched cross-ply laminates. Further, the first experimental picture approves the assumption that the transverse cracks have been fully developed and hence a layer scale stiffness reduction can be applied.

Figure 11 (a) Damage patterns observed in the tests.

Figure 11 (b) Simulated damage patterns.

The stress concentrations change with the development of NIS. It was shown that the stress concentrations increase with the development of transverse cracks. The stress concentrations are defined as the stress ratios of the local stresses against the far-field average applied stress on the whole laminate. An advantage of this definition is that the disturbance of a failure event on the local stresses can be calculated directly from the numerical simulations. Figure

12 presents the stress concentration evolution including the effect from transverse cracks and local delamination, which are calculated from the stresses in the mid-plane of the 0° layers. It should be noted that the local delamination (NID) has been modeled in the same way as discussed above for transverse crack and for NIS. Its effects on the local stress concentrations in the critically loaded 0° layers are also included in Figure 12. First of all, the calculations predict a uniform stress zone next to the notch, after the NIS is fully developed, see Figure 12 (b), the initial part of Figure 12 (a). Secondly, the formation of NIS, together with the effect of the transverse cracks and local delamination, will alleviate the very high local stress concentration at the notch root, and hence the final stress concentration is reduced to about 3.1 in the critically damaged materials of the longitudinal layers. Combining the far-field average stresses, it is not difficult to estimate the local stresses in the critical damage zone. Thirdly, the stress concentrations tend to a relatively constant value at about 0.6 % to 0.8 % applied far-field strain.

Figure 12 (a) Stress concentration evolution with the applied strain: local stress decreases with the NIS growth.

Figure 12 (b) The initial part of Figure 12(a) local stress decreases with the NIS growth.

5. Conclusion remarks

A progressive failure approach was constructed and applied to study the failure process of notched composite laminates. The constructed numerical strength model is capable of taking the local matrix failures into account on a meso-scale when the local stresses are evaluated. The occurrences of the various fracture mechanisms and their interaction are also taken into account in the stress evaluation. Particularly, the simulation here gives a sense of the evolution of the matrix-dominated failures and their interactions under a non-uniform tensile stress field caused by the notches and modified by the occurred matrix failures. The influence of damage on the stress in the critical 0° fibres at the notch root is established. This explains the fact that composites are less sensitive to notches than it would be concluded based on linear elastic theory.

REFERENCES

- [1]. Lekhnitskii, S.G., “Anisotropic Plates”, New York, NY: Gordon and Breach. 1968.
- [2]. Whitney, J. M. and Nuismer, R. J., “Stress Fracture Criteria for Laminated Composites Containing Stress Concentrations”, *J. of Comp. Mater.*, Vol. 8 (1974), pp. 253 – 265.
- [3]. Nuismer, R.J. and Whitney, J.M., “Uniaxial failure of Composite Laminates Containing Stress Concentrations”, *ASTM STP 593* (1974), pp117-142.

- [4]. Kim, R.Y., "Initiation of free-edge delamination in composite laminates" in *Key Engineering Materials Vol. 37* (1989) pp.103-136.
- [5]. Karlak, R.F., "Hole effects in a related series of symmetrical laminates" in *Proceedings of Failure Modes in Composites IV*, edited by Ornie, J.A. and Crossman, F.W., Chicago, IL, 1977, pp.105-117.
- [6]. Waddoups, M.E., Eisenmann, J.R., and Kaminski, B.E., "Macroscopic fracture mechanics of advanced composite materials", *J. Composite Materials*, 5, (1971), pp. 446-454.
- [7]. Krueger, R., O'Brien, T.K., "A shell/3D modelling technique for the analysis of delaminated composite laminates", *Composites Part A* 32 (2001), pp.25-44.
- [8]. Parvizi, A., Garrett, W. K. and Bailey, J. E., "Constrained cracking in glass fibre-reinforced epoxy cross-ply laminates", *J. Materials Science*, **13** (1978), pp.195-201.
- [9]. Liu C.J., Sterk, J.C., Nijhof, A.H.J., and Marissen, R., "Matrix-dominated damages in notched cross-ply composite laminates: experimental observations", *Applied Composite Materials*, **9** (2002), pp. 155-168.
- [10]. Carlsson, L.A., Gillespie, J.W. and Tretheway, B.R., "Mode II interlaminar fracture of graphite/epoxy and graphite/peek", *J. Reinforced plastics and Composites*, Vol 5, pp. 170-187.